

BASELINE STUDY ON GRADE 12 STEM STUDENTS' COMPETENCY LEVEL AND THEIR SOURCES OF DIFFICULTIES ON KINEMATICS GRAPHS INTERPRETATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 2

Pages: 235-242

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2954

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14729482

Manuscript Accepted: 12-31-2024

Baseline Study on Grade 12 STEM Students' Competency Level and their Sources of Difficulties on Kinematics Graphs Interpretation

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Abstract

This study examines the competencies of Grade 12 STEM students in interpreting motion graphs, employing a quantitative-qualitative descriptive methodology. A designed 20-item multiple-choice test was administered to evaluate students' understanding of position-time and velocity-time graphs. The findings reveal that both male ($\bar{x} = 7.85$, $s = 2.08$) and female ($\bar{x} = 7.59$, $s = 2.08$) students demonstrate a "Beginning" level of competency in graphical analysis of motion. Notably, students exhibited significant challenges, particularly with items related to position vs. time graphs; for instance, item 16 achieved a high correct response rate of 95.00%, while items 8 and 12 reflected only 5.00% accuracy. These results underscore substantial gaps in students' grasp of kinematics concepts, which are attributed to limited instructional time and emphasis. Consequently, the researchers advocate for remedial classes concentrating on motion graph interpretation and suggest a comprehensive curriculum review to ensure essential topics receive adequate attention. Furthermore, they recommend conducting similar studies with a larger sample size to enhance the reliability of the findings.

Keywords: *position-time graph, velocity-time graph, graphical analysis, kinematics concepts*

Introduction

Science education, like many other disciplines, aims to cultivate essential skills that are applicable in real-world contexts (Cagande & Jugar, 2018). Within the field of Physics—a discipline often perceived as challenging and abstract (Blickenstaff, 2010)—one crucial skill for comprehending and mastering concepts is the ability to discern trends and visualize patterns through graphical representations (Beichner, 1994). According to Ergul (2018), skills such as graph identification, graph drawing, and graph interpretation are fundamental tools in both mathematics and science courses. In this information age, graph interpretation is particularly vital (Chang et al., 2024), extending its usefulness beyond science and mathematics to our everyday lives. One primary reason for the significance of understanding graphical representations is that graphs facilitate the interpretation of quantitative data that is encountered frequently (Nilyani et al., 2022). Instances, where graphs play a crucial role, include news reports that depict trends in global events, weather graphs illustrating temperature fluctuations, rainfall, or typhoon patterns, and medical graphs that showcase the effectiveness of new treatments against various diseases. Moreover, businesses utilize sales graphs to assess product performance and political polling data is often presented in graphical form during elections. Thus, graphs are integral not only to science but also to daily life, as we frequently engage with information displayed through graphs and other visual representations.

Inscriptions are visual representations utilized by scientists and other professionals as part of their endeavor to develop scientific theories and explain real-world phenomena (Roth & M.K., 1998). Such inscriptions encompass maps, symbols, lists, tables, models, equations, and graphs. This process falls under the umbrella of data visualization, defined by Bybee (2010), Donnelly-Hermosillo et al. (2020), and Ow-Yeong et al. (2023) as a branch of data science that employs graphs, charts, or diagrams to represent data. Pozzer and Roth (2003) further classified these inscriptions into two categories: those with more contextual details, characterized as “real” or “concrete,” and those with less contextual detail, labeled as “abstract.” Graphs are categorized within the latter group, indicating that they offer less detailed information while remaining among the most used representations. This raises an intriguing question regarding the irony of why scientists and other professionals rely on abstract inscriptions, particularly graphs, to understand and explain the complexities of the real world.

Why do graphs matter?

According to Glazer (2011), competencies in graph interpretation, together with skills in data organization and analysis, have emerged as pivotal factors influencing individuals' understanding of contemporary society. The ability to create and interpret graphs is essential not only for students in the field of physics but also across various disciplines (Ruf et al., 2023), as these skills are fundamental to experimental practices central to the scientific method (McKenzie & Padilla, 1986).

Additionally, graphs facilitate the rapid recognition of trends in physical phenomena, aligning with Mokros and Tinker's (1987) assertion that graphs enhance visual pattern recognition among scientists and students, enabling them to identify trends and differences effectively. Kelly, Jasperse, and Westbrook (2005) contend that graphs are generally more accessible than repetitive numerical data, complex tables, or verbose narratives.

They present multiple advantages of utilizing graphs over other visual formats, such as high information density without loss of data, rapid assimilation of overall results, and the capability to depict complex relationships among multivariate data in multiple dimensions. Beyond serving as an efficient means for summarizing large datasets, graphs empower individuals to infer underlying processes and

interactions within systems through the examination of individual data points (Shah & Hoeffner, 2002), facilitating predictions of future trends as well.

Esach (2013) emphasizes that graphical representations, such as graphs, are integral to scientific practice, particularly within the field of physics. This sentiment is echoed by Tesla et al. (2002), who assert that many fundamental areas of physics are virtually impossible to address effectively without graphic representations. Nilyani et al. (2022) support this perspective and encourage educators to cultivate graph interpretation skills in students, asserting that inadequate graphic literacy considerably hinders students' comprehension of physics concepts, particularly those related to motion.

Boote (2014) further reinforces this notion by highlighting that reasoning about graphical representations, establishing connections between variables on the horizontal and vertical axes (such as time and distance), creating graphical representations, critically evaluating data presented in graphs, and employing graphs to communicate findings are vital components of higher-order thinking skills in both science and mathematics.

Given the wealth of research emphasizing the significance of developing graph interpretation skills, PISA recognizes this competency as a vital 21st-century workforce skill. This recognition underscores the necessity of nurturing these skills in students, particularly in today's technology-driven world, where a lack of graph literacy may hinder professional advancement (Redding, 2014).

In this context, Bowen and Roth (2012) identify essential competencies that students should master in reading and creating graphs and other visual inscriptions. These competencies include the ability to describe and represent relationships using tables, graphs, and formulas; analyze functional relationships to elucidate how changes in one quantity affect another; systematically collect, organize, and summarize data; estimate and make measurements to describe and compare phenomena; construct, read, and interpret tables, charts, and graphs; make inferences and present compelling arguments based on data analysis; evaluate arguments rooted in data analysis; represent situations and numerical patterns through various formats—including tables, graphs, verbal rules, and equations—and explore the interconnections among these representations; and finally, analyze tables and graphs to identify properties and relationships. Developing these skills is crucial for fostering a thorough understanding of data representation and analysis, which is essential for success in both academic and professional arenas.

Graph utilization in kinematics: The science of motion

Researchers strongly emphasize the development of students' ability to construct, comprehend, and utilize data visualizations (Donohoe & Costello, 2020) as it constitutes a vital form of literacy known as data visualization literacy (DVL). Graphs serve as essential communication tools in educational settings due to their significant applications not only in science but across various areas of learning. One notable area in physics that employs graphs, particularly line graphs, is Kinematics, the study of motion. Kinematics is a fundamental topic in general physics, and problems related to this field are frequently represented in graphical form (Sarkity, Azhar, & Sundari, 2022).

Graphs are widely used in subjects such as mathematics and science to convey crucial information. In physics, four primary types of graphs are commonly utilized: the comparison line graph, the compound graph, the Cartesian plane graph, and the scatter graph. Among these, the line graph is the most frequently employed in high school physics, especially in the context of Kinematics. According to Bell and Javier (1989), line graphs pose a greater challenge for learners compared to other types of graphs, as they require students to grasp that the line on a Cartesian graph represents the relationship between two variables.

As an introductory component of physics education, Kinematics has garnered considerable attention regarding what and how much students learn from this subject. Researchers speculate that this area may have attracted more interest than others because it serves as a foundational "building block" for understanding more complex concepts (Beichner, 1994). Despite the extensive attention kinematics has received, most literature in educational research highlights that misinterpretation of kinematic graphs represents a significant challenge for students at various academic levels.

Students' performance in graph interpretation

Numerous studies indicate that graph interpretation is a complex and multifaceted process, with various factors increasing the difficulty of graphical comprehension. For instance, Phage, Lemmer, and Hitage (2017) noted that the complexity of graphs—particularly the number of variables involved and the relationships and interactions among them—along with students' mathematical proficiency significantly contributes to the challenges learners face when interpreting graphs. Graphs are commonly utilized in solving mathematical and physics problems; however, despite efforts to familiarize students with graphical problems, Handhika et al. (2019) found that students struggle to solve math problems presented in graphical form. This challenge extends to physics courses as well.

Erceg and Aviani (2014) discovered that students encounter difficulties in understanding graphs that present physical quantities indirectly. Furthermore, a lack of skills in reading and interpreting graphs adversely impacts students' success in physics, as noted by Planinic et al. (2012). Kinematics, in particular, is an area where students tend to perform poorly in examinations, especially on questions involving graphs. Mucholobwe and Mutambo (2023) referred to a report from the Examination Council of Zambia, which indicated that from 2016 to 2020, students aspiring to pursue science-related careers demonstrated poor performance in physics examinations, particularly in interpreting motion graphs.

The findings of Rosenquist and McDermott (1987) also reveal that many students need help with solving kinematic problems due to their inability to interpret motion graphs accurately. More specifically, Jones (1983) reported that students have difficulty grasping the qualitative and quantitative definitions of acceleration and velocity, as well as the relationship between these two variables. Additionally, Taylor and Loverude (2018) found that students often need help to differentiate between position, velocity, and acceleration. Similarly, Sarkity, Azhar, and Sundari (2022) highlighted that students face challenges in identifying the motion of objects on velocity-time and position-time graphs, particularly in cases of negative velocity, attributing these challenges to a lack of understanding of the concepts of velocity and acceleration.

In addition to the various challenges students face when interpreting kinematic graphs, several common issues have been identified that significantly hinder their ability to grasp this critical concept. One prominent issue is students' misunderstanding of the relationship between slope and height, which often leads to confusion in interpreting graphical data. Many students also mistakenly view graphs as mere pictorial representations of events, overlooking the deeper mathematical relationships they depict. Additionally, there is a prevalent difficulty in determining the slope of curves that do not pass through the origin, which complicates their comprehension of graph behavior. Students frequently struggle to interpret the area under a curve, which is essential for understanding concepts such as displacement and velocity. This confusion extends to slope interpretation itself, where students may mix up concepts such as area and gradient. Finally, issues with the construction of graphs further compound these challenges, as students may need to understand how to represent their data accurately and clearly. Collectively, these issues create significant barriers to students' understanding of kinematic graphs and their applications in physics. It is important to note that the difficulties associated with kinematics graphs extend beyond students to pre-service and in-service teachers as well. Isik et al. (2012) found that pre-service classroom teachers struggled to relate kinematics graphs to real-life scenarios effectively. Bowen and Roth (2005) revealed that primary and secondary school science pre-service teachers required significantly more practice and experience to enhance their data and graph interpretation competencies.

Given the importance of graphing skills and the increasing interest in students' interpretation of kinematics graphs, there is a pressing need for assessment and re-evaluation of these skills. Various studies have shown that both learners and teachers encounter challenges when dealing with motion graphs in kinematics. While experts may find learning from multiple representations relatively straightforward, students often face complexities in connecting elements across these representations. Nonetheless, multiple representations possess great potential for enhancing students' understanding of physics concepts. Guentulle et al. (2024) suggest that students learn more effectively when problems incorporate multiple representations, ultimately improving their overall learning outcomes.

Research Questions

The purpose of this baseline study is to look into the level of competence of grade 12 STEM students and the common sources of difficulties they encounter on motion graph interpretation. Specifically, this study will answer the following questions:

1. What is the competency level of grade 12 STEM students in interpreting motion graphs in kinematics?
2. What are the factors affecting students' level of competency in interpreting motion graphs in kinematics?

Methodology

Research Design

The purpose of this quantitative-qualitative descriptive study is to evaluate the motion graph interpretation competency of grade 12 students enrolled in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand. To assess the students' performance and learning outcomes, we will utilize a combination of a standardized test and a researcher-developed assessment consisting of 20 items. The scores from these assessments will provide insights into the students' understanding and mastery of concepts related to position-time and velocity-time graphs.

Participants

The study was conducted at a Senior High School Department in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, which represented a vibrant educational setting that promoted effective learning for its students. The department was strategically located at the heart of the university, enhancing its accessibility and influence.

Complementing the nurturing and supportive environment of the senior high school department was the building that housed the faculty, staff, and principal's office, providing a centralized space that facilitated communication and collaboration among educators and administrators.

The Senior High School Department offered a diverse array of academic tracks, including the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Strand, the Humanities and Social Sciences (HumSS) Strand, the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) Strand, and the General Academic Strand (GAS). Under the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Track, two strands were available: the Home Economics (HE) Strand and the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Strand. Additionally, the department offered the Arts and Design (AD) Track. This wide range of options enabled students to explore their interests and develop their skills, effectively preparing them to pursue their academic and professional aspirations.

Instrument

The study utilized a 20-item multiple-choice test as the primary research instrument. This test included questions derived from two key sources: the Test of Understanding Graphs in Kinematics (TUG-K) and examinations administered to Grade 12 STEM students. The TUG-K, developed by Robert Beichner, evaluates students' proficiency in interpreting kinematic graphs. Since the TUG-K was not specifically designed for the General Physics 1 curriculum applicable to Grade 12 STEM students, the researchers undertook modifications by revising, omitting, and adding questions to ensure the test was appropriately aligned with the curriculum.

Making the Test Questionnaire

The TUG-K assesses seven objectives related to the concepts of slope and area under the curve through a total of 20 items. Objectives 1 and 2 concentrate on slope, evaluating students' understanding of velocity as represented in position-time graphs and acceleration as depicted in velocity-time graphs. Objectives 3 and 4 focus on analyzing changes in position and velocity, respectively, by examining velocity-time and acceleration-time graphs. Finally, Objectives 5, 6, and 7 evaluate the comprehension of slope and area under the curve using various methods, including the selection of corresponding graphs, interpretation of textual descriptions, or the generation of graphs based on provided textual information.

Table 1. Description of the 21 items of the original TUG-K grouped by each of the 7 objectives (Beichner, 1994)

Objective	Item(s)	Description
1	5, 17, 13	Determine positive and negative values of velocity from the position graph, and the highest instantaneous velocity.
2	7, 6, 2	Determine positive values of acceleration from the velocity graph and the interval with the most negative acceleration.
3	18, 4, 20	Establish and determine changes in position from the velocity graph.
4	10, 16, 1	Determine the smallest, general, and greatest changes in velocity from the acceleration graph.
5	11, 14, 15	Select the corresponding graph from position, velocity, and acceleration graphs.
6	8, 3, 21	Evaluate specific cases such as movement that includes stopping, backward motion, and constant velocity from the position graph, and constant acceleration from the velocity graph.
7	9, 12, 19	Identify graphs that represent positive and constant acceleration, constant velocity, and constant non-zero acceleration from textual descriptions.

In the context of the K-12 curriculum, interpreting kinematics graphs is a part of the learning competencies, especially in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics strand. The curriculum guide for General Physics 1 identifies the following learning competencies related to interpreting motion graphs (DepEd, 2019):

Table 2. Learning competencies in General Physics 1 curriculum guide (DepEd, 2019)

Code	Learning Competency
STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-14	Interpret displacement and velocity, respectively, as areas under velocity vs. time and acceleration vs. time curves
STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-15	Interpret velocity and acceleration, respectively, as slopes of position vs. time and velocity vs. time curves
STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-16	Construct velocity vs. time and acceleration vs. time graphs, respectively, corresponding to a given position vs. time-graph and velocity vs. time graph and vice versa

The multiple-choice test was designed to evaluate students' comprehension of specific learning competencies. By modifying questions from the TUG-K framework and incorporating items crafted by educators, the researchers developed a comprehensive assessment aligned with the General Physics 1 curriculum for Grade 12 STEM students.

Recognizing that the TUG-K was not originally intended for the context of the General Physics 1 curriculum for Grade 12 STEM, the researchers adjusted the questionnaire by modifying, omitting, and adding questions. Ultimately, the researchers constructed a 20-item multiple-choice test, featuring four answer choices instead of the five presented in the original TUG-K. This test included both adapted questions from the TUG-K as well as questions derived from exams specifically designed for Grade 12 STEM students.

Table 3 provides a detailed breakdown of the 20-item multiple-choice test, including the sources, descriptions, and any changes or modifications:

Table 3. Summary of multiple-choice test items, including sources, descriptions, and competencies.

Subtopic	Test Items	Description	Related Competencies
Analyzing Position vs. Time Graphs	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6,	These items involve interpreting motion characteristics (velocity, acceleration, direction) from position vs time graphs	STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-15
	9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15		STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-16
Analyzing Velocity vs. Time Graphs	7, 8, 10, 16, 17, 18, 19	These items involve interpreting velocity and acceleration characteristics from velocity vs. time graphs	STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-14 STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-15

Interpreting and Constructing Graphs	20	This item involves translating information between position vs. time, velocity vs. time, and acceleration vs. time graphs	STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-15 STEM_GP12KIN-Ib-16
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The researchers' strategy of modifying, omitting, and adding questions led to the development of a test that effectively assesses the learning objectives of the General Physics 1 curriculum, while also addressing the educational needs of Grade 12 STEM students. This comprehensive assessment approach provides a strong foundation for evaluating students' understanding of kinematics graphs.

Procedure

The systematic method employed in this study's data collection procedure was designed to gather information from grade 12 STEM students. The primary objectives of this procedure were to evaluate the students' proficiency in interpreting kinematics graphs and to identify the sources of any difficulties they encountered in this subject.

The first step in this approach involved obtaining permission from the instructor overseeing the research process. This ensured that the study was conducted in accordance with established standards and ethical guidelines. Following the approval, the researcher informed the participants about the data collection methodology, which facilitated the students' ability to provide informed consent and understand the research context.

Subsequently, a test was administered to the twelfth-grade STEM students. This test was specifically designed to assess the students' understanding of kinematics graph interpretation and was developed by educators to meet standardized criteria. To determine the sources of the challenges faced by the students in interpreting kinematics graphs, the researcher collected the test questionnaires, organized the data, and conducted a thorough analysis and interpretation of the results.

Data Analysis

The researcher assessed the competency levels and identified the sources of difficulties in interpreting kinematic graphs among the respondents by calculating the means and standard deviations of their scores. The mean scores were then converted using the transmutation table provided in DepEd Order No. 8, Series of 2015.

To qualitatively interpret the mean scores, the researchers employed the proficiency levels outlined in DepEd Order No. 73, Series of 2012.

Table 4. Reference for Competency Level from DepEd

Level	Equivalent Numerical Value
Beginning	74% and below
Developing	75%-79%
Approaching Proficiency	80%-84%
Proficient	85%-89%
Advanced	90% and above

Frequency and percentage distributions are used to determine the proportion of the students who got the correct answer in each item.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, discussions, and personal insights that the researchers have gathered through the investigation of the study on graphical analysis.

Students' level of competency in motion graph interpretation

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of the Scores

	Mean Score	SD	Transmuted Score (%)	Qualitative Description
Male	7.85	2.08	69.40	Beginning
Female	7.59	1.72	69.20	Beginning
Overall	7.67	1.82	69.30	Beginning

Legend: 90% and above (Advanced); 85%-89% (Proficient); 80%-84% (Approaching Proficiency); 75%-79% (Developing); 74% and below (Beginning)

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics for students' scores on the Graphical Analysis of Motion Test. The male students (mean = 7.85, standard deviation = 2.08) and female students (mean = 7.59, standard deviation = 2.08) demonstrate comparable levels of competence in this topic. Overall, the students are classified as operating at the Beginning level of competency in Graphical Analysis of Motion.

These results indicate that students possess insufficient knowledge of analyzing position-time and velocity-time graphs. Consequently, remediation activities should be implemented to enhance students' understanding of Graphical Analysis of Motion.

Table 6 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of students who answered each item correctly. The results indicate that item number 16, which pertains to the position versus time graph, has the highest percentage of correct responses (f = 38, P

= 95.00%). Conversely, items 8 and 12, both focused on position versus time graphs, show the lowest percentage of correct answers ($f = 2$, $P = 5.00\%$). Items 4, 5, 6, and 20 also demonstrate a favorable percentage of correct responses. However, student performance is notably poor on items 8, 11, 12, 13, 17, 18, and 19.

Table 6. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Correct Answer per Item*

<i>Item No.</i>	<i>Type of Item</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
1	Position vs Time	5	12.50
2	Position vs Time	20	50.00
3	Position vs Time	6	15.00
4	Position vs Time	37	92.50
5	Position vs Time	34	85.00
6	Position vs Time	34	85.00
7	Velocity vs Time	17	42.50
8	Position vs Time	2	5.00
9	Position vs Time	12	30.00
10	Position vs Time	7	17.50
11	Velocity vs Time	3	7.50
12	Position vs Time	2	5.00
13	Position vs Time	3	7.50
14	Position vs Time	21	52.50
15	Position vs Time	26	65.00
16	Position vs Time	38	95.00
17	Position vs Time	3	7.50
18	Position vs Time	3	7.50
19	Position vs Time	3	7.50
20	Velocity vs Time	32	80.00

Factors affecting learners' level of competency in interpreting motion graph

The following factors, as perceived by the subject teacher, influenced students' competency in interpreting motion graphs:

The teacher's emphasis on interpreting kinematics graphs was limited due to time constraints in the curriculum. This presents an opportunity to integrate more focused instruction on this topic to enhance student understanding.

Many students experienced challenges in retaining information about the topic, attributed to the significant time gap between when the material was taught and when assessments occurred. This observation highlights the potential benefit of reinforcing key concepts through periodic reviews or supplementary materials to facilitate better retention and comprehension.

By addressing these factors, instructors can develop strategies to improve student competency in interpreting motion graphs, ultimately fostering a deeper understanding of kinematics.

Conclusions

The study revealed that students are at a beginning level in their ability to interpret position-time and velocity-time graphs. Despite the teacher's diligent efforts to optimize the limited instructional time available for covering essential competencies in General Physics 2, students did not fully grasp many of the fundamental concepts related to kinematic graphs. However, this highlights an opportunity for targeted intervention and enhanced instructional strategies to improve students' understanding of these critical concepts in the future.

One of the primary concerns of physics educators is effectively delivering a range of competencies within a limited timeframe. To address this challenge, the researchers advocate for the implementation of remedial classes specifically focusing on the interpretation of motion graphs. This targeted approach will enhance students' understanding of the material, enabling them to engage deeply with the lessons.

Additionally, it is essential to review the competencies covered in subjects such as physics. This review will ensure that each topic receives adequate attention, thereby preserving the quality of learning that occurs in the classroom.

Furthermore, the researchers recommend conducting a similar study with a larger sample size to enhance the reliability of the findings. This approach will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced in physics education and the effectiveness of the proposed interventions.

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